

MODELLING STEAM METHANE REFORMER OPERATION WITH HYDROGEN-ENRICHED FEEDSTOCK

Hoppej D.¹, Variny M.¹, Kondáš R.¹

¹ Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia
dominik.hoppej@gmail.com

Abstract

Natural gas enrichment by renewable hydrogen belongs to key tools in reaching the ambitious decarbonization goals set by the European Union. Problems related to the renewable hydrogen production, its co-transport with natural gas and combustion properties of hydrogen-natural gas mixtures are researched intensely. Less attention is paid to the consequences of consumption of such gas mixtures in steam reformers – important natural gas consumers for industrial hydrogen production. Available studies recommend and assess hydrogen pre-separation. While possible, it is quite costly, especially regarding the inevitable presence of a large pressure gradient, whether in membrane or adsorption-desorption separations, coupled with large power requirements for the recompression of the low-pressure effluent. This stimulated the presented study devoted to assessing the operation of an industrial steam methane reformer with hydrogen-enriched feed and comparing the energy and carbon footprint of hydrogen production from conventional and enriched feed. Key findings are obtained, indicating which way of hydrogen recovery is more cost-effective and more environmentally friendly: whether hydrogen pre-separation or routing the hydrogen-enriched feed to the steam reformer.

Introduction

Blending green hydrogen in the natural gas pipelines is one of key tools in reaching ambitious decarbonization goals set by European Union^{1,2}. While most of scientific work dedicated to blending natural gas with hydrogen is focused on possible associated risks, as its leakage³, or steel pipeline integrity⁴, the aim of this work is to examine consequences of feedstock composition change, considering feasible hydrogen content of up to 15 vol. %⁵ for steam methane reforming process. This process is the most common technology of hydrogen production⁶. In this work, 2 scenarios are compared, among them the hydrogen separation from the natural gas before its usage in the process, and direct usage of hydrogen enriched feedstock in the steam methane reforming process. In addition, third, theoretical scenario of delivering hydrogen equivalent to hydrogen blended in the natural gas to the natural gas pipelines was analysed.

Modelling of hydrogen plant

As the aim of developed model was to evaluate the impact of blending hydrogen to the natural gas on steam methane reforming process, existing hydrogen plant was used as the template for mathematical model, using the available documentation of this plant. Scheme of developed model can be found in Figure 1. To avoid unnecessary robustness of model, several assumptions were considered, which we believe will not serve as serious bottlenecks for the interpretation of obtained results. Among these assumptions, or simplifications, was the perfect combustion at the furnace of reforming reactor. Also, due to the low content of odorization substances in natural gas and low impact on the plant energy balance, the process of desulphurization was neglected in terms of reactor simulation and instead was simulated by addition of heat exchanger, with the same temperature (15 °C) and pressure loss (50 kPa), as was projected for this process.

Preparation of reaction mixture in this plant consists of the addition of recycled stream of hydrogen to natural gas in device M_ZP-H, and subsequent compression (K-100), and desulphurization of natural gas (DSU) after preheating in the heat exchangers (CONV_D1 and CONV_D2) of convective section of the furnace of reforming reactor. After desulphurization, natural gas is blended with high pressure steam and heated in CONV_A before entering the reforming reactor REF at projected temperature. Molar ratio of natural gas and stream was set to 3, in accordance with projected ratio. Reforming reactor, filled with Ni-containing catalyst, which operates in temperature 850 °C favours reactions (1) and (2).

Figure 1. Scheme of mathematical model in Aspen Hysys V11.

Before the reaction mixture enters high temperature shift reactor (HTS) it is cooled down in steam generator, SGREF, below 400 °C. HTS reactor is filled with Fe-based catalyst, selective towards reaction (3).

Reforming reactor and high temperature shift (HTS) reactor were modelled with the use of ATE. This parameter allows us to assess the influence of uneven heat and mass transfer, uneven velocity profile and mixing intensity, distribution of catalyst, etc., on the final composition of reaction mixture. Comparison of calculated and projected composition on the outlet of reforming reactor and HTS reactor can be observed in Table I. Reaction mixture at the outlet of HTS is then cooled down in high pressure steam generator (SGREF), feed water heater (FWH_HTS) and low-pressure steam generator (LP_SG). Low pressure steam is utilized in consequent process, where the steam present in reaction mixture is condensed at COOLER and separated in W_SEP. Condensed steam is then stripped using low pressure steam, which was, however, not our object of interest, due to negligible impact on process energy consumption.

After separation of condensed water the reaction mixture is processed in pressure swing adsorption process (PSA-H2), where the hydrogen is separated and the process tailgas (PSA-OFF) is combusted in the FURNACE, together with natural gas. Flue gas delivers heat in radiation section of the reforming reactor (RAD) and then is cooled down at the convective section of the furnace, consisting of heat exchangers preheating reaction mixture (CONV_A, CONV_D2, CONV_D1) and air (A-H) and steam generator (CONV_C), as well as steam heater (CONV_B). Heat exchangers and steam generators present in hydrogen plant, were modelled assuming constant value of heat transfer coefficient, nondependent on the flowrate changes.

Methodology

To achieve main goals, simulations with natural gas containing 0, 5, 10 and 15 volume % of hydrogen were performed. For hydrogen content higher than 5 vol. % a stream of recycled hydrogen used for desulphurization of natural gas stopped and the amount of process steam was changed, to limit steam to carbohydrates ratio equal to 3.0. Due to the rise of volume flow of natural gas and consequent increase of pressure losses, calculated using Darcy law, the outlet pressure of produced hydrogen decreased. However, as the designed pressure of hydrogen is higher, than the pressure of hydrogen pipelines network, it was not necessary to increase the outlet pressure of feed compressor. Still, as the volume flow is increased, electricity consumption of feed compressor rises, which was taken into account when calculating the price of produced hydrogen. Changes of natural gas consumption and steam production were also considered. To sustain constant steam production, compensation mechanism of central power plant was considered, which increases its steam output to compensate decrease of steam production in plants of refinery. The consumption of natural gas in the central power plant was also considered, as well as its carbon dioxide emissions - the impact of hydrogen presence in the natural gas on total

carbon dioxide emissions was also observed. The price of produced hydrogen was calculated for maximum capacity of hydrogen plant.

For the economy analysis, price of long-term contracts for the natural gas were taken⁷. Due to observed correlation between the natural gas and electricity prices of long-term contracts, price of electricity was assumed to be 2.5 times higher in comparison with natural gas price. For the emission allowances, current price was taken⁸, as of 14.4.2022. Necessary for the analysis was to determine the price of natural gas blended with hydrogen. Our assumption was to use the same price per heating value of blended natural gas, as current prices of long-term contracts suggest and add the costs to produce hydrogen. As hydrogen used for blending should be made off renewable energy sources, energy consumption of electrolysis was considered, at 48 MWh/t of hydrogen⁹. Prior to the economic analysis, hydrogen content was considered as the equivalent of the natural gas used up for the electricity production for water electrolysis process, with 40% thermic efficiency, in accordance with the assumption of electricity price correlation.

Price of produced hydrogen was thus calculated as the sum of costs of natural gas, emission allowances for the emitted carbon dioxide and electricity consumed in the feed compressor. From this sum, the equivalent costs for natural gas consumption at the central power plant were deducted. For the scenario with the separation unit, energy consumption for the separation was added and the price of separated green hydrogen was deducted from the hydrogen price, as it could be transferred to the market for the price of green hydrogen, in accordance with the assumptions in previous section. This was also the case for the last scenario, which assumed delivery of green hydrogen directly from the stream of produced hydrogen. Price of the green hydrogen present in the natural gas used as the process feed was thus deducted from the price of produced hydrogen.

Analysis of hydrogen separation from the natural gas before its usage in the process was based on the results of study aiming at the optimization of this separation process¹⁰. This study develops separation process for the 80% yield of hydrogen and 99.97% purity of separated hydrogen, high enough to be used in fuel cells. with the energy consumption dependant on hydrogen content, as can be seen in the Table I.

Table I
Separation process electricity consumption¹⁰

Hydrogen content of natural gas [vol. %]	Energy consumption [kWh of electricity/m ³ of H ₂]
1	2.2
4	0.6
10	0.4

Results

As can be observed in the Table II, despite the decrease in the natural gas consumption, hydrogen presence in the natural gas has a significant impact on total energy consumption if the hydrogen production costs are included. As reaction rate of reforming reactions decreases due to higher hydrogen content of natural gas, less heat is consumed in the reforming reactor. Consequently, less natural gas is combusted in the furnace of the reforming reactor, which results in the decrease of steam production. This decrease is compensated by the increase of central power plant emissions, which were also considered, when calculating total carbon dioxide emissions – as we can see in Table II, total carbon dioxide emissions decrease, as lower natural gas consumption and lower emission factor of natural gas blended with hydrogen has incomparably higher impact on the process emissions. Power consumption of feed compressor increases, but as can be seen, this effect has very little impact on final price of produced hydrogen. Still, the price of produced hydrogen rises significantly.

The second scenario was based on separation of green hydrogen from the natural gas before its usage in the steam reforming process. Results of this analysis can be observed in the Table III.

Due to high yield of proposed separation process, residue hydrogen content of natural gas after the separation was reduced to the amount smaller than the amount used for desulphurization. Thus, changes of steam production, CO₂ emissions and compressor power consumption were not observable. Separated hydrogen was then, in accordance with the proposed usage in the article, sold for the price of green hydrogen, to compensate for higher price of purchased natural gas blended with hydrogen.

Following the results obtained by simulations with natural gas blended with hydrogen, economic analysis was performed, results of which can be observed in Table II.

Table II
Results of direct usage scenario

Natural gas H ₂ content (vol. %)	Natural gas consumption / H ₂ as natural gas eq. (kWh/kg)	Steam production (kWh/kg)	CO ₂ emissions (kg/kg)	Separated H ₂ as NG eq. (kWh/kg)	Price of produced H ₂ (€/kg)
0	55.856 / 0.000	5.729	10.099	-	5.345
5	+ 0.869 / 2.878	+ 0.027	- 0.051	2.566	+ 0.103
10	+ 2.023 / 6.080	+ 0.110	- 0.046	5.468	+ 0.232
15	+ 3.258 / 9.662	+ 0.189	- 0.045	8.780	+ 0.365

Table III
Results of hydrogen separation scenario

Natural gas H ₂ content (vol. %)	Natural gas consumption / H ₂ as natural gas equiv. (kWh/kg)	Steam production (kWh/kg)	CO ₂ emissions (kg/kg)	Compressor power consumption (kWh/kg)	Price of produced H ₂ (€/kg)
0	55.856 / 0.000	5.729	10.099	0.116	5.345
5	- 0.319 / + 2.818	- 0.093	- 0.226	+ 0.001	+ 0.216
10	- 0.500 / + 5.815	- 0.145	- 0.418	+ 0.006	+ 0.459
15	- 0.773 / + 9.003	- 0.214	- 0.630	+ 0.011	+ 0.712

As hydrogen present in the natural gas is not changed in the process, the third scenario was considered, to deliver part of produced hydrogen back to the natural gas grid. Still, the hydrogen from the natural gas combusted in the furnace of reforming reactor was not delivered back to the natural gas grid. This approach allows us to compensate higher prices, similarly as in the previous scenario. Despite lack of legislative backup, the simulations of this scenario were performed, and results can be seen in the Table IV.

Table IV
Results of hydrogen delivery back to the natural gas grid scenario

Natural gas H ₂ content (vol. %)	Natural gas consumption / H ₂ as natural gas eq. (kWh/kg)	Separation power consumption (kWh/kg)	Separated H ₂ as natural gas eq. (kWh/kg)	Price of produced H ₂ (€/kg)
0	55.856 / 0.000	-	-	5.345
5	+ 0.934 / 2.881	0.140	2.305	+ 0.167
10	+ 1.970 / 6.075	0.197	4.860	+ 0.331
15	+ 3.239 / 9.641	0.312	7.713	+ 0.525

Table V
Comparison of hydrogen prices according to analysed scenarios

Natural gas H ₂ content (vol. %)	Direct usage (€/kg)	Hydrogen separation (€/kg)	Hydrogen delivery back to the natural gas grid (€/kg)
0	5.345	5.345	5.345
5	5.561 / + 4.03 %	5.513 / + 3.13 %	5.449 / + 1.94 %
10	5.805 / + 8.59 %	5.676 / + 6.19 %	5.577 / + 4.34 %
15	6.058 / + 13.32 %	5.871 / + 9.83 %	5.711 / + 6.83 %

Main setback of this scenario is reduction in productivity of hydrogen, as part of produced hydrogen is delivered to the natural gas grid. That is the reason, why the results in Table IV are different from the results in Table II. This influences natural gas consumption, as well as steam production and CO₂ emissions. Still, due to significant reduction of non-compensated consumption of green hydrogen, price of produced hydrogen is lower in comparison with previous scenarios.

Comparison of obtained prices of hydrogen produced in accordance with each scenario can be observed in Table V. As results from this table, delivery of hydrogen back to the natural gas grid is the most feasible way of mitigation of negative economic effects of hydrogen presence in the natural gas from the economic point of view. By this approach it is possible to compensate higher prices of natural gas, without consuming surplus electricity for separation of hydrogen.

Conclusion

Despite hydrogen delivery back to the natural gas grid scenario being the most economically feasible way of usage of natural gas blended with hydrogen for hydrogen production, it has setbacks. At first, lack of legislation enabling this option makes it purely hypothetical. It also results in the decrease of hydrogen production, as part of produced/processed hydrogen is taken back to the natural gas grid. Scenario with hydrogen separation before its usage in the process is slightly less economically feasible, but it has drawbacks of its own. The biggest issue could be connected to the market size – due to low number of fuel-cells powered vehicles currently on the road, demand for green hydrogen could be the most serious problem for this scenario. Considering direct usage of natural gas blended with hydrogen, hazard analysis is necessary, as this was not among the aims of this study. Also, as higher flowing velocities impact reaction time, ATE parameter, which was calculated for conventional natural gas, would have had different value. Due to this, another work is needed to be performed, using rigorous model for reforming reactor, which is being prepared.

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References

1. HYDROGEN EUROPE, Vision on the Role of Hydrogen and Gas Infrastructure on the Road Toward a Climate Neutral Economy, 2019. In [online]. [cit. 13-06-2022]. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/hydrogen_europe_-_vision_on_the_role_of_hydrogen_and_gas_infrastructure.pdf>
2. Mahajan D., Tan K., Venkatesh T., Kileti P. Clayton C. R.: *Energies* 15, 3582 (2022).
3. Hormaza Mejia A., Brouwer J., Mac Kinnon M.: *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 45(15), 8810 (2020).
4. Bouledroua O., Hafsi Z., Djukic M. B., Elaoud S.: *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 45(35), 18010 (2020).
5. Fraunhofer Institute for Energy Economics and Energy System Technology, The limitations of hydrogen blending in the European gas grid, 2022, ECF, Berlin
6. Kafková V., Karas D., Cyprichová V. *Vodík*. Centrum Výskumu a Vývoja, Leopoldov 2021.
7. PXE - Zemní plyn - ceny a grafy PXE zemního plynu, vývoj ceny PXE zemního plynu 1 MWh - 1 rok - měna EUR | Kurzy.cz
8. EU Carbon Permits - 2022 Data - 2005-2021 Historical - 2023 Forecast - Price - Quote (tradingeconomics.com)
9. Machhammer O., Bode A., Hormuth W.: *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 39(6), 1185 (2016).
10. Liemberger W., Halmschlager D., Miltner M., Harasek M.: *Appl. Energy* 233-234, 747 (2019).